

collaboratively settled reasonable time and place. Adopting a constructivist approach to feedback, introducing qualitative changes in the feedback process, and improving student feedback literacy might help the learners to understand and make effective use of feedback.

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THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TOOLS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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***Abstract.** The author discusses the variability and features of using modern information technologies to teach English to primary school students. The article highlights the importance of using ICT in foreign language education and raises the question of possible options for their use.*

Key words. Internet; communicative and psychological adaptation; listening; level of education; pedagogical innovations; information technology.

Introduction. Currently, it is necessary to receive information from different sources, use it and create it independently. The widespread use of ICT opens up new opportunities for teachers in teaching a foreign language. Information technologies, as a rule, are technologies that use such technical means as audio, video, computer, Internet. Currently, multimedia technologies are widely used. The term “multimedia” means “many environments”. Such information environments are: text, sound, video. Software products that use all these forms of information presentation are called multimedia.

Main Part. The use of ICT in the process of teaching English helps to ensure the “integrity” of the lesson - the implementation of educational, upbringing and developmental goals of training, as well as the principle of differentiation and integration. ICT helps to activate students' cognitive activity, stimulates and develops cognitive processes: thinking, perception, memory. The use of ICT in English lessons allows students to master the main types of speech activity in a bright, interesting form: reading, speaking, listening, writing, to consolidate the material in an interesting form, using disks, slides, videos, which contributes to a clear perception of the material on a particular topic. Also, the positive aspects of the presence of ICT in the educational process include an increase in the level of education, the quality of students' knowledge, and the growth of the teacher's professional competence.

It should be noted that ICT helps to achieve specific goals of teaching English in primary school.

Formation of communication skills in English, taking into account the speech capabilities and needs of schoolchildren. To achieve this goal, the following forms of ICT are used: creation of multimedia presentations. Their use in the learning process has the following advantages:

- implementation of visual perception of the material;

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- the ability to demonstrate various objects using a multimedia projector and projection screen;
- combining audio, video and animation effects into a single presentation helps to compensate for the volume of information received by children from educational literature.

Of course, we should not forget that the best educational effect from the use of information and communication technologies, in particular presentations, is achieved in subject teaching when they are used in combination with other active methods and personality-oriented teaching technologies and are limitedly included in the lesson scenario.

2. Development of personality, speech abilities, attention, thinking, memory, motivation for further mastering of the English language. For example, the use of a multimedia projector allows to significantly increase the clarity of the lesson (pictures, slides, videos), which contributes to the development of motivation. Phonetic games and tasks are used to develop attention. For their implementation, voiced and illustrated texts of fairy tales, songs, dialogues in English are used.

3. Ensuring communicative and psychological adaptation of students to the new linguistic world in order to overcome the psychological barrier in the future and use English as a means of communication. In order to achieve communicative and psychological adaptation of younger students, the principle of “language guess” is used in primary school. When studying verbs, the capabilities of the computer allow the most accurate reflection of the meanings of words (using animation, video, pictures, etc.). In addition, students can create applications from photographs, pictures printed on a printer, texts typed on a computer.

4. Introducing children to a new social experience using the English language. Fostering a friendly attitude towards representatives of other countries. Achieving this goal is facilitated by familiarization with the history of the country of the language being studied (individual work of students at the computer), the inclusion

of voiced and illustrated rhymes in English in outdoor games (using a multimedia projector).

The use of ICT allows the teacher to create their own tests of varying complexity, with the help of which you can objectively assess the child's knowledge. When working on the computer, students are happy to complete such tasks as: "Insert the missing letters", "Help decipher the enchanted word", "Match the words" and others. Traditionally, the study of the topic ends with repetition, consolidation and generalization. All these elements can be combined by offering students at the final stage of each topic to create a multimedia project, a presentation (two or three slides). By creating a presentation, students get an excellent opportunity to systematize the acquired knowledge and skills, their practical application, as well as the opportunity to realize their intellectual potential and abilities. It is very important for students to feel an interest in independent creative work.

Using ICT in English lessons in primary school, we see that all children with different speech abilities are actively involved in educational activities, more willingly complete various tasks, learn to listen and understand oral and written speech.

With all this, it is necessary to remember that work with children of primary school age should be based on the principle of "do no harm" and be aimed at maintaining health, emotional well-being and developing the individuality of each child.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it is necessary to emphasize that the introduction of information technologies into the educational process does not at all exclude traditional teaching methods, but is harmoniously combined with them at all stages of training: familiarization, training, application, control. But the use of information technologies allows not only to repeatedly increase the effectiveness of training, but also to stimulate students to further independent study of English.

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USING TECHNOLOGY TO ENHANCE PROBLEM-SOLVING ACTIVITIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING FOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** This article explores the integration of technology in foreign language teaching for high school students. By incorporating tools such as game applications, collaborative platforms, and multimedia resources, teachers can enhance problem-solving skills while making language learning more engaging and practical. These technologies not only improve vocabulary building and grammar comprehension but also develop critical thinking, creativity, and real-world communication skills. The article highlights the impact of technology on language learning and classroom applications, emphasizing the importance of balancing technology with traditional teaching methods.*

***Keywords.** Technology, foreign language teaching, problem-solving, high school learners, gamified learning, collaborative platforms.*

Introduction. Technology is one tool that supports language learners so that they use the target language in culturally appropriate ways to perform authentic